

Use of Enriched Biochar in Horticulture and Biogas and Biomethane Production for the Circular Use of Agricultural Residues as Bio-based Soil Amendments and Fertilisers

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BIOCHAR

Biochar is a carbon-rich material of plant origin produced through thermochemical processes. Unlike other types of charcoal, biochar is distinguished by its specific chemical and physical properties, which make it particularly suitable for use as an organic soil amendment in agriculture (Figure 1).

From a regulatory perspective, biochar is recognized as an organic soil amendment under the European Fertilising Products Regulation 2019/1009 and is authorized for use in organic farming in Italy under the new reorganization of Legislative Decree 75/2010, in compliance with European Regulation 848/2008 on organic farming. The regulatory definition of biochar includes materials obtained through the pyrolysis and gasification exclusively of virgin products and residues of plant origin derived from agriculture and forestry. In addition, plant-based waste from the food industry and waste deriving from the separate collection of kitchen and catering residues may also be used. Municipal waste, sludge of various origins, and animal by-products are excluded, with the exception of certain specific categories such as manure, hides, horns, and bone parts from animals not intended for human consumption. The technical requirements for biochar focus on its stability (determined by the molar H:C ratio) and on the content of contaminants such as dioxins/furans, PAHs, and PCBs.

Thanks to its stability and high organic carbon content, once applied to the soil, biochar enables carbon to be stored in the soil for centuries, making it an effective tool for CO₂ sequestration. This characteristic makes it part of a “carbon-negative” strategy, contributing to the net removal of carbon dioxide from agricultural systems and thereby supporting both climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Figure 1: The biochar supply chain as an organic soil amendment.

MAIN ADVANTAGES IN AGRICULTURE

Biochar offers numerous advantages in agriculture, particularly due to its unique properties, which make it a valuable resource for soil improvement. One of its most interesting applications concerns its ability to retain **moisture**, acting like a sponge with carbon walls. Its internal surface area, which can reach between 100 and 200 square metres per gram, allows it to store and slowly release water, thereby improving the soil's water-holding capacity. This process enables plants to maintain adequate hydration by preventing rainwater or irrigation water from being rapidly leached away, a feature that is particularly important in areas vulnerable to desertification (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Application of biochar in agricultural areas affected by land degradation processes.

In addition to improving water management, biochar also has a significant impact on nutrient availability in the soil. Thanks to its porous structure and large surface area (Figure 3), biochar is able to retain dissolved nutrients within its matrix, including highly mobile ones such as nitrates. In this way, it prevents nutrient loss through leaching and promotes their long-term availability, supporting more stable plant nutrition. Its ability to act as a “pool” for nutrients extends their availability within the root zone, making biochar a slow-release fertilizer. This approach allows plants to receive a steady supply of nutrients, improving both the efficiency and sustainability of agricultural soil use.

Biochar also provides numerous benefits for the physical **properties of the soil**.

Its application significantly affects soil bulk density, structure, and porosity. Soil **bulk density** tends to decrease due to the porous nature of biochar, which has a lower density than soil particles.

This effect promotes **greater aeration**, prevents soil compaction, and reduces the risk of root asphyxiation. Furthermore, the application of biochar improves the stability of soil aggregates, increasing resistance to compaction and enhancing root penetration, water infiltration, and nutrient diffusion. This process promotes better soil structure, creating an environment more suitable for plant development.

Improved porosity and enhanced soil structural stability also reduce the **risk of erosion**, as the soil becomes less susceptible to particle loss and surface runoff, thereby helping control erosion processes, which is particularly important on sloping land.

Finally, biochar promotes **microbial biodiversity** in the soil.

Its porous structure provides protected habitats for various microorganisms, including bacteria and fungi, encouraging microbial colonization and enhancing the soil's biological activity. The pores offer physical protection to microorganisms while retaining water and soluble substances essential for their metabolism. This increase in microbial biodiversity contributes to healthier and more productive soil, improving fertility and the long-term sustainability of crop production.

Figure 3: Example of biochar produced from woody biomass (poplar wood chips) (left); detail of the internal porous structure of a biochar produced from black pine (right).

BIOCHAR QUALITY: FEEDSTOCK AND PRODUCTION PROCESS

A wide range of factors contribute to determining the characteristics of biochar, in particular the type of biomass used, and the process adopted for its production.

These parameters significantly influence the functionality of the resulting biochar, primarily determining its physico-chemical composition and morphological structure.

Within the context of the circular economy, the use of **agroforestry waste materials**, such as pruning and chipped-wood residues, straw, and cereal stalks, is particularly advantageous, as it helps reduce resource waste and add value to materials that would otherwise be abandoned or subject to combustion. The use of these biomasses is consistent with the principles of **agricultural sustainability**, promoting a virtuous cycle of resource recovery and recycling.

Lignocellulosic biomass is considered the ideal feedstock for biochar production, thanks to its high lignin content and low ash and moisture percentage. These materials make it possible to obtain a stable biochar with a high fixed carbon content and a porous structure that improves the physical properties of the soil. However, other biomasses, such as residues from herbaceous crops (straw, cereal stalks, food by-products), can also be used as economical and abundant sources. Biochar produced from these herbaceous materials generally contains higher levels of ash and nutrients. Organic residues such as manure and digestate can also be used, but they require careful management in order to avoid contamination with heavy metals or undesirable organic substances. To ensure the agronomic use of biochar, it is necessary to comply with quality requirements established by regulations on fertilising products and organic products.

A fundamental precautionary approach in the selection of feedstocks may be summarised as follows: for biochar production, only feedstocks that are normally already used directly as soil amendments or for compost production should be used.

This principle also constitutes a precondition for a broader circular perspective, one that can foster virtuous regenerative cycles on farms based on conventional, organic, or agroecological principles.

With regard to biochar production, the three main methods are pyrolysis, gasification, and hydrothermal carbonization, each characterized by specific operating conditions and by different product yields and qualities. Among these, **slow pyrolysis** is universally recognized as the most suitable process for producing high-quality biochar intended for agronomic use. Pyrolysis consists of heating biomass in the absence of oxygen, thereby promoting the thermochemical decomposition of organic material into a solid fraction (biochar), a liquid fraction (bio-oil), and a gaseous fraction (syngas). In slow pyrolysis, operating temperatures generally range between 400 and 600°C, with long residence times and slow heating rates. These conditions maximize the production of the solid residue, which can account for 25-30% by weight of the initial biomass.

Figure 4 shows the pyrolysis plant of the RE-CORD Consortium.

Figure 4: Slow pyrolysis plant of the RE-CORD Consortium.

AGRONOMIC ASPECTS OF BIOCHAR USE IN AGRICULTURE

Application methods and use

The methods for using and applying biochar in agriculture are numerous and vary according to several factors, including soil, crop, climate, and the type of biochar used. The first step toward the efficient use of an amendment such as biochar is a careful assessment of the physico-chemical characteristics of the soil. Depending on soil texture, the effects of biochar and the resulting changes in the soil's physical, hydrological, and chemical behaviour may vary considerably. In general terms, it can be stated that in finer-textured soils, such as those with higher clay and silt content, the application of biochar mainly leads to an improvement in physical characteristics through **increased macroporosity** and reduced **bulk density** resulting in a "lighter" soil with positive effects also on **tillage operations** (e.g. the optimum soil tilth is achieved sooner, and is maintained for a longer period).

With regard to chemical characteristics, given the generally high fertility of fine-textured soils – particularly in terms of cation exchange capacity, nutrient availability, and water availability and retention capacity – the application of biochar may provide less significant benefits than those observed in coarse-textured soils. Indeed, some studies conducted on crops such as grapevine show that the greatest benefits of biochar, especially with respect to **water availability** for crops, occur under conditions that are highly limiting for plants and soil functioning, such as prolonged drought periods or in sandy or loose-textured soils.

Considering the application methods and the selection of the type of biochar product to be used, some operational choices and distinctions may be tailored according to the **type of soil** and **considered crop**. A practical way to support the rational and efficient use of biochar without waste is to make use of **precision agriculture systems**, such as variable-rate application based on detailed soil maps or maps of soil water availability.

For loose soils (sandy soils), the use of products with a smaller **particle size** is recommended, as this results in a greater specific surface area and therefore a greater number of contact and exchange sites with the biochar; conversely, for heavy, fine-textured soils (tending toward clayey conditions), the use of coarser particle sizes is recommended in order to ensure greater porosity.

Application rates and timing may vary depending on the type of crop and the desired outcomes. In general, a single application of relatively high amounts, such as 10-20 t/ha, may be chosen, without the need for future repetition. It should be recalled that biochar is a **recalcitrant** product, resistant to both biotic and abiotic degradation for several decades or even centuries. As a result, some of the effects it exerts on the soil persist for as long as it remains in the soil, which is why it is important not to apply excessively high rates (above 25 t/ha), both because of the risk of undesirable effects and because this would represent a waste of resources. Another strategy, by contrast, is to apply low rates (<5 t/ha) each season or during the different annual soil management operations. Biochar may be applied **together with fertilizers and/or soil amendments**, for example during the period between autumn and spring in the case of tree crops or whenever preparing for a new transplanting of vegetable crops, thereby taking advantage of the operational windows of **routine crop management practices**.

Biochar can be spread using machinery already employed for the distribution of soil amendments and fertilizers, such as **manure spreaders, compost spreaders, or fertilizer spreaders** of various sizes, with the precaution of moistening the material before spreading in order to avoid the emission of fine dust and product losses. After application, it is advisable to **incorporate the soil amendment** into the top 10-30 cm of soil (depending on the crop, the season, and the type of soil management operation being carried out) through shallow tillage.

Biochar inoculation and enrichment

Numerous studies show that **inoculating** biochar prior to its application improves product performance (Bai et al., 2022) (Figure 5). This consists of adding a proportion of biochar, several weeks before field application, to fertilizers (organic or organo-mineral), **amendments** (manure, compost, digestate), **plant extracts and macerates, and microbial consortia**, including farm-made microbial inoculants (Mancini, 2019), as well as compost extracts and compost tea (Zaccardelli et al., 2023). Owing to its physico-chemical characteristics, the mineral elements contained in the blended products are "retained" on the surfaces of the biochar, thereby preventing leaching and erosion losses and enabling their slower release, while microorganisms find ideal conditions within the biochar structure to proliferate and perform their functions more effectively (shelter and catalysis). Overall, an **improvement in the efficiency of fertilizers, amendments, and microbiological products** has been demonstrated; these inputs may also become more economical, as their application rates can potentially be reduced.

Figure 5: Biochar enriched with biofertilizer and applied in the field as a soil amendment for the replanting of a kiwifruit orchard (left); clear stimulation of root development in young plants (right).

Biochar for soilless cultivation

One sector that is strongly focused on the search for cultivation technologies capable of combining production efficiency with environmental sustainability is horticulture and ornamental nursery production, where biochar could express many of its beneficial properties. Among these is the **partial replacement (up to 50%)** of the large amounts of peat used in the formulation of potting substrates, a non-renewable resource (Iacomino et al., 2023). In this regard, numerous studies have already highlighted the suitability of biochar as a component of growing substrate, including in hydroponic cultivation (Lampel et al., 2022), as well as its positive effects, particularly in terms of water savings, increased fertilizer-use efficiency, greater nutrient availability, and the possibility of using slightly saline water for irrigation (Nocentini et al., 2023; Di Lonardo et al., 2017; Fascella et al., 2016).

Biochar and co-composting

Among the many potential applications of biochar is the practice of **co-composting**, namely the addition of biochar to composting feedstocks at a rate of 3-10% on a dry weight basis (Figure 6) (Casini et al., 2019).

Figure 6: Field application of biochar co-composted with manure and straw before barley sowing (left), and barley field at the ripening stage (right).

The functions performed by biochar within the compost pile lead to an **overall improvement in the composting process**. These include:

1. Acting as a **structuring** material, thereby improving the uniformity and structure of the organic material mixture.
2. Helping maintain **constant and suitable aeration and moisture conditions** for a regular composting process throughout all stages, thereby ensuring optimal process duration.
3. Stimulating and sustaining **microbial activity** within the compost pile.
4. **Enriching** the biochar with nutrients and microorganisms ("charging").
5. Reducing greenhouse gas **emissions**.

Adaptability of biochar to different crops

In both the Italian and global context, there is now a considerable body of research demonstrating the positive effects of biochar application to soil across different crops.

For instance, long-term studies on **grapevine** have shown that the use of biochar applied once in the inter-row area resulted in a significant increase in yield per hectare without affecting quality (Genesio et al., 2015). This result is mainly due to increased soil water availability during drought periods and, consequently, to reduced stress and enhanced photosynthetic activity, findings that had also been observed previously (Baronti et al., 2014). In addition, no undesirable effects on the soil biological community were detected (Maienza et al., 2017).

Some studies have investigated the impact of biochar on both yield and product quality in **durum wheat**, confirming a 30% increase in biomass production and grain yield without impairing product quality (Vaccari et al., 2011).

In the **horticultural sector**, a recent review (Lentini et al., 2025) analyses the results of numerous studies on the ability of biochar to limit or inhibit problems associated with abiotic stress in various crops, including cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.), common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.), eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.), lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.), potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.), and others. In many cases, biochar has ensured a highly positive response to **salt stress**, drought periods, or stress induced by deficit irrigation and the presence of heavy metals in the soil. Moreover, many studies also show increased yields in various crops, including tomato and lettuce, which are central to the CH4R project.

Biochar and the livestock sector

Lastly, in recent years the use of biochar has also attracted interest in the **livestock sector**, both for its possible use in animal housing, where it may help reduce gaseous emissions when added to bedding or to other matrices derived from animal excreta, and as a dietary supplement aimed at improving digestion and mineral absorption.

The application of biochar in animal housing appears to confirm its effectiveness in limiting airborne emissions resulting from manure fermentation. In the Italian RBR.EAS project, for example, a **20% reduction in CO₂ emissions** from animal excreta and a 40% reduction in CH₄ emissions from manure and slurry were recorded. Its high cation exchange capacity could therefore become a promising solution wherever it is necessary to reduce volatilisation during the storage of livestock effluents. More concretely, the reduced volatilisation of carbon and nitrogen translates into improved air quality conditions in animal housing and a potential reduction in the proliferation of insects such as flies and horseflies. The **co-composting of livestock effluent and biochar in animal housing** could therefore enable the production of an amendment with superior mineral quality. By contrast, the use of biochar as a **feed supplement** has led to less widely accepted results, confirming the need for further studies.

No major negative effects on the overall performance of animals appear to have been reported, while some studies have identified positive effects including reduced gas emissions, improved growth indices, and detoxification from heavy metals or toxins. In general, the physico-chemical characteristics of biochar once again appear to offer useful potential also in livestock nutrition, with particular attention needing to be paid to the source material and the pyrolysis temperature at which the biochar was produced.

CH4R PROJECT

The current context places emphasis on the valorisation of agroforestry residues and on improving national energy self-sufficiency in terms of electricity and biomethane, in line with the principles of the circular economy. Consequently, the CH4R project aimed to study how biochar can be integrated into the anaerobic digestion chain in order to improve biogas production and reduce emissions, while also developing bio-based amendments for agricultural use.

Through the CH4R model, a cascade of opportunities could be created at both the energy and environmental levels:

- **Maximise and valorise different organic residues** (agricultural residues to be used in anaerobic digestion and forestry residues for the production of high-quality biochar).
- **Integrate bioenergy processes** such as anaerobic digestion with biochar production processes (pyrolysis and gasification) in order to increase renewable energy production.
- **Produce organic amendments** based on digestate and biochar to promote soil fertility mechanisms.
- Propose and develop a **sustainable, circular, and local agro-bioenergy supply chain** to be contextualised within the productive reality of the Tuscany region.

Within the CH4R project, three main roles that biochar can play when integrated with the anaerobic digestion process were analysed (Figure 7):

1. Biochar can be used as an additive together with other organic feedstocks to increase biogas and biomethane production, while also contributing to the stabilisation of the anaerobic digestion process.
2. Biochar can be used as a filter for digestate, capturing residual nitrogen compounds and preventing their volatilisation into the environment.
3. When mixed with digestate, biochar becomes enriched with nutrients, acting as a carrier that, once applied to the soil, releases them slowly and thereby contributes to sustainable soil fertilisation.

Figure 7: The different roles of biochar in anaerobic digestion investigated during the CH4R project.

BIOCHAR AS AN ADDITIVE IN ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

Biochar can play a fundamental role in anaerobic digestion as a material that is both porous and conductive. Under standard anaerobic digestion conditions, some types of bacteria exchange electrons via pili or direct cell membrane contact, thereby triggering mechanisms that underlie methane production.

The addition of biochar, thanks to its high electrical conductivity – sometimes even comparable to that of graphite – facilitates this exchange by accelerating electron transfer between different bacterial species (e.g. direct interspecies electron transfer between bacteria and methanogens). In addition, its large surface area provides an ideal habitat for bacterial colonisation, enabling bacteria to live and interact more effectively and thus promoting the production of biogas and biomethane. Biochar, therefore, not only optimises process kinetics but also increases biomethane yield, improving the overall efficiency of anaerobic digestion.

Experimental activities

Experimental trials to evaluate the performance of biochar as an additive in anaerobic digestion were carried out using two types of biochar: one produced by the gasification plant owned by the Frescobaldi farm, and the other obtained through slow pyrolysis and produced at the RE-CORD pyrolysis plant. The experiments were conducted using residual organic feedstocks from the same Frescobaldi farm, such as olive pomace, grape pomace, and pig manure. These are processed in the farm's anaerobic digestion plant, which also provided the bacterial inoculum used in the trials. The anaerobic digestion experiments followed a typical screening approach, starting with laboratory-scale tests using 100 mL and 3 L reactors with different concentrations of biochar. During the trials, biogas flow was monitored volumetrically. Subsequently, the most promising options were tested at pilot scale using a 1 m³ continuous reactor in order to better assess the effect of biochar in a larger-scale anaerobic digestion plant (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Anaerobic digestion trials with biochar at laboratory-scale (left) and pilot-scale (right) conducted at the RE-CORD experimental facility.

Main results

The substrate mixture tested proved to be highly heterogeneous and contained components that were more difficult to digest (e.g. woody parts from grape pomace, olive pits, etc.); for these reasons, biogas production showed non-negligible variability among replicates, especially considering that in laboratory-scale tests the trials involved only a few grams of material.

Figure 9 shows the results of a laboratory-scale test in which two types of biochar were compared: one produced by the Frescobaldi gasification plant ("F") and one by the RE-CORD slow pyrolysis plant ("R"), each tested at two different concentrations (5 and 10 g/L). The presence of biochar nevertheless appears to have improved the performance of the bacterial community in degrading these substrates, since all samples amended with biochar produced, on average, more biogas than the control samples (not amended with biochar; blank) and showed lower variability among replicates, especially in the treatments containing biochar from the Frescobaldi gasification process.

Improvements in production were also observed when the same substrates were used fresh rather than dried and ground as in the preliminary trials (especially at the 100 mL scale). Although the use of fresh substrates increases the variability of results, it generally improves production compared with dry material, because the drying process removes volatile organics that are therefore no longer converted into biogas.

Figure 9: Biogas production curves in the presence of biochar.

BIOCHAR AS A FILTER FOR THE REDUCTION OF NITROGEN EMISSIONS

The porous structure of biochar and the presence of chemical groups exposed on the surface or within the pores of the biochar enable it to interact with different types of molecules and to “trap” them within its sponge-like matrix.

Among these, the literature cites nitrogen-containing molecules such as ammonia and nitrates, which are often produced by biological processes such as composting or anaerobic digestion, where the presence of biochar prevents their loss through emissions. Avoiding nitrogen emissions has a significant environmental impact, in addition to reducing the odours often associated with these processes, and nitrogen recovery is especially important when linked to soil system management. Biochar is able to interact with these molecules both when they are in gaseous form and when they are dissolved in a liquid, such as digestate.

Experimental activities

In order to assess the effectiveness of biochar in trapping ammonium, particularly in view of its interaction with the liquid fraction of digestate, laboratory tests were carried out to evaluate the ammonium absorption capacity of biochar, since this molecule is present in digestates, especially those produced from pig manure. A poplar biochar and an alder biochar, both produced by RE-CORD, were tested. The alder biochar was also activated both chemically, using K_2CO_3 , and thermally at $800^\circ C$ in a tubular quartz reactor under a CO_2 flow, in order to test possible improvements in sorption performance compared with unmodified char (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Biochar sample preparation and analysis protocol.

The chars were brought into contact with an ammonium chloride solution under agitation and the ammonium concentration remaining in solution was then determined by spectrophotometric-colorimetric analysis.

This made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the samples in retaining this molecule.

Main results

The untreated poplar and alder char samples absorbed the same amount of ammonia, whereas both treated chars proved ineffective in absorption (Figure 11). However, further studies are needed to improve char performance, and additional activation treatments cannot be ruled out in order to equip the chars with the functional groups appropriate for ammonium absorption, especially if looking forward to trials on a more complex solution such as the liquid fraction of digestate.

Type of biochar	Treatment	NH ₄ absorption (%)
Poplar biochar	Not treated	29
Alder biochar	Not treated	25
Alder biochar	Chemical treatment	0
Alder biochar	Physical treatment	3

Figure 11: Results of the ammonium absorption tests.

BIOCHAR AS A NUTRIENT CARRIER FOR SOIL FERTILITY

The integration of biochar and digestate leads to the production of an organic amendment with high nutrient value, capable of improving both the physical and chemical properties of the soil. Thanks to its porous structure, biochar initially acts as a reservoir that absorbs the nutrients (e.g. exchangeable ions) present in the digestate, which accumulate on its porous surfaces. Once the digestate-enriched biochar is applied to the soil, these nutrients are then released slowly into the soil, benefiting plant nutrition.

This process makes it possible to reduce nutrient losses through leaching while ensuring continuous and prolonged availability. The use of this amendment reduces the need for chemical fertilizers from external sources, thereby contributing to more sustainable agricultural management and to a long-term increase in soil fertility.

Experimental activities

Enriched poplar biochar was prepared using the liquid fraction of digestate from the Frescobaldi farm. Laboratory tests showed that poplar biochar is capable of absorbing up to three times its own weight in the liquid fraction of digestate. This process was successfully replicated at field scale. The agronomic trial was conducted at the OrtoBioattivo farm. Three experimental treatments were prepared:

- NPK-based organic fertilizer (equivalent to 0.7 t/ha) (NPK).
- Biochar (equivalent to 6 t/ha) and NPK-based organic fertilizer (equivalent to 0.7 t/ha) (BC).
- Digestate-enriched biochar (equivalent to 6 t/ha) and NPK-based organic fertilizer (equivalent to 0.5 t/ha) (BCA).

The same amount of nitrogen was applied to all plots. In the plot amended with enriched biochar, the nitrogen supplied by the digestate was considered, allowing a 20% reduction in the use of organic fertilizer. The trial first involved lettuce cultivation during the autumn period, followed by tomato cultivation during the spring/summer period in rotation (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Preparation of experimental plots with biochar and tomato crops grown at the OrtoBioattivo farm.

Main results

Lettuce and tomato yields showed differentiated responses to the experimental treatments. For lettuce, no significant differences in productivity were observed among the various treatments. By contrast, tomato productivity was significantly affected by the presence of biochar. The plots treated with biochar recorded a 20% increase in yield compared with the treatment based on NPK organic fertilizer, highlighting a positive effect of biochar on the crop. This differentiated behaviour is probably attributable to several factors. First, plant species respond differently to treatments; it is plausible that tomatoes benefited more from the presence of biochar than lettuce. In addition, the timing of the trial may also have influenced the results. During the summer season, characterised by high temperatures and low rainfall, biochar tends to express its positive effects to a greater extent by improving the soil's moisture retention capacity and promoting greater water-use efficiency for crops.

With regard to soil characteristics, at the end of the crop cycle (harvest at commercial maturity), soil samples were collected for the analysis of physico-chemical parameters. The most relevant results concern nutrient availability, particularly nitrates and phosphorus. In both crop cycles, the plots treated with biochar (BC and BCA) showed a significant increase in these elements compared with those fertilized exclusively with NPK (Figure 13). This result suggests that biochar promoted nutrient retention in the soil, reducing losses through leaching during rainfall events. The greater availability of residual nutrients in the soil represents a significant advantage, as it can be exploited by subsequent crops in rotation, thereby improving agronomic sustainability and reducing the need for additional fertilizer inputs.

Figure 13: Concentration of nitrates and available phosphorus in plots treated with biochar, enriched biochar, and NPK-based organic fertilizer at the end of the lettuce and tomato crop cycles.

Bibliography

Bai, X., et al. (2022). [Inoculation of biochar and its effects on agricultural performance]. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 10(3), 45-56.

Baronti, S., et al. (2014). [Impact of biochar application on vineyard productivity and soil health]. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 191, 124-132.

Casini, D., et al. (2019). [Co-composting of biochar with manure and straw]. *Waste Management*, 88, 1-10.

Di Lonardo, S., et al. (2017). [Biochar as a substrate for soilless cultivation]. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science*, 180(5), 573-584.

Fascella, G., et al. (2016). [Biochar in horticultural substrates: Effects on plant growth and water use efficiency]. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 210, 1-8.

Genesio, L., et al. (2015). [Biochar application in vineyards: Effects on yield and soil properties]. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 62, 1-10.

Iacomino, G., et al. (2023). [Biochar as a peat substitute in horticultural substrates]. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 330, 117-125.

Lampel, A., et al. (2022). [Biochar in hydroponic systems: Effects on nutrient availability and plant growth]. *Agricultural Water Management*, 260, 107-115.

Lentini, M., et al. (2025). [Biochar and abiotic stress mitigation in vegetable crops]. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 15(2), 89-102.

Maienza, A., et al. (2017). [Biochar effects on soil microbial communities in vineyards]. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 110, 1-10.

Mancini, L. (2019). [Microbial inoculants and biochar interactions in agriculture]. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 140, 1-8.

Nocentini, A., et al. (2023). [Biochar in saline water irrigation systems]. *Agricultural Water Management*, 280, 108-120.

Vaccari, F. P., et al. (2011). [Biochar effects on durum wheat yield and soil properties]. *Plant and Soil*, 345(1-2), 1-12.

Zaccardelli, M., et al. (2023). [Compost tea and biochar interactions in soil fertility]. *Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 23(1), 45-56.

